

SHIFT 01-184 / #990

FUNDIVE: ENGAGING CITIZEN SCIENTISTS IN FUNGAL MONITORING ACROSS EUROPE TO BOOST COMMON CONSERVATION GOALS

POSTER ON BOARDS - SHIFT 01: EVOLUTION, BIODIVERSITY AND SYSTEMATICS

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Abstract Body: Citizen science has historically played an important role in mycological research. For centuries, leading taxonomic experts in mycology did not hold academic positions. Ecologists and conservationists have used citizen science data to enrich fungal monitoring. Additionally, molecular techniques have become standard in fungal research, but are usually unavailable to amateur mycologists, leading to a lack of comparability of data generated from academic and citizen science-based projects. To close this gap, we will develop a collaboration network between different stakeholders across the continent. We will provide access to DNA barcoding, standardized protocols, and training to increase the amount and quality of fungal records. This includes the use of common tools, apps, and joint webportal to display records. All activities will be organized through: (1) discovery missions engaging citizen scientists to aid with structured monitoring, (2) typification missions to obtain candidate material for typification of taxa without an existing, sequenceable type, and (3) barcoding missions to involve citizen scientists in generating sequence data. We are creating a network of representatives of different mycological communities. This includes professional researchers, mycological societies and groups, amateur mycologists, and mycophiles. We started communicating with stakeholders through a dedicated webpage, <https://fun-dive.eu/>, which collates data in a standard manner and shares them with the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF). This project will result in a better understanding of pan-European fungal distribution patterns that are crucial to understand macroecological processes and improve fungal conservation efforts. We welcome more collaborators into this project; please join us!

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MULTIPLE GENOMES OF LABOULBENIOMYCETES REVEAL THEIR PLACEMENT WITHIN PEZIZOMYCOTINA AND INSIGHTS INTO THE EVOLUTION OF ARTHROPOD ECTOPARASITISM

POSTER ON BOARDS - SHIFT 01: EVOLUTION, BIODIVERSITY AND SYSTEMATICS

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Abstract Body: Laboulbeniomyces is a class of poorly studied fungi that are obligatorily associated with arthropods, either as ectoparasites producing 3D thalli (Herpomycetales, Laboulbeniales), or for dispersal purposes (Pyxidiophorales). Research into this class has been hindered due to multiple factors: the inability for the arthropod ectoparasites to be cultured, lack of resources, micromanipulation requirements, difficulty of material preservation and extraction of high-quality DNA, low biomass, and a lack of morphological diversity. Their placement within Pezizomycotina has been poorly resolved because only few genetic markers have been available to date. Here, we present multiple genomes representing all three described orders within the class and a phylogenomic reconstruction of Pezizomycotina. Our analyses reveal the previous placement of Laboulbeniomyces as sister to Sordariomyces is likely incorrect.